

Policy Brief and Key Findings from the H2020 COMFORT project:

Tipping Points and Regime Shifts in Regional Marine Ecosystems

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The EU should promote nature-based solutions to tackle climate change, whilst intensifying efforts to reduce GHG emissions through renewable energy, energy efficiency, and sustainable practices. Carbon dioxide removal (CDR) techniques, like afforestation and ocean fertilization, although may remove small amounts of CO₂, should not replace GHG emission reduction efforts. Before implementation, their effectiveness, risks, and limitations such as high costs, large-scale deployment and environmental impact must be thoroughly assessed.
2. Develop and implement policies to address ocean acidification, warming, and oxygen depletion in all European Seas. This includes measures to limit carbon emissions, pollution, and regulate fishing, along with the establishment of long-term regional monitoring programs. Implementation of the sustainable management plan addressing these threats is critical in improving the ecological status and resilience to future climate change
3. To effectively address the risks and vulnerabilities facing European marine ecosystems, it is critical to thoroughly assess the impacts of climate change, pollution, and other stressors. Adaptation plans based on the assessments should promote the resilience of marine ecosystems to these threats and incorporate conducting biodiversity surveys, developing early warning systems for ocean acidification and warming, and implementing measures to reduce nutrient inputs and other pollutants that harm marine life.
4. The EU can promote sustainable fisheries in the tropics with stakeholders by supporting adaptation solutions through e.g. "discard ban" and "landing obligation" (the EU Common Fisheries Policy 2013). Regional policies should account for species redistribution due to climate change with improved data collection, and resource management to prevent overfishing such as e.g. the European Data Collection Framework and measures towards illegal, unreported, and unregulated (IUU) fishing (e.g. vessel monitoring systems, satellite tracking, and port controls). These actions support long-term sustainability and maintain healthy ecosystems.
5. The EU's goal of achieving a 55% reduction in GHG emissions by 2030, is ambitious and necessary to align with the Paris Agreement to limit global warming. Furthermore, a net-zero emissions target by 2050, with interim goals, will further reinforce the EU's commitment to mitigating the multiple threats posed by climate change to the Arctic and other regions, including warming, acidification, and extreme events. Considering the urgent need to address these impacts on the environment, it is necessary for the EU to further strengthen collaborations with the world's largest emitters to accelerate the green transition together towards achieving the 55% target.

KEY MESSAGES

- A tipping point in the North Atlantic Ocean currents lies at a temperature increase of up to 3.5°C, the current global warming is at ~1.1°C
- The subpolar currents of the North Atlantic already experienced a tipping point ~700 years ago leading to rapid ocean circulation changes in response to melting glaciers and Arctic Sea Ice, the same processes occur at an accelerated rate nowadays
- Implementation of the Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) methods after exceeding the Paris Agreement temperature targets may lead to circulation changes with significant negative impacts in the surrounding regions

Please note that regions are only indicative, not precise. Figure modified from Heinze et al., PNAS 2021. Licence: 4.0 (CC BY)

- The maximum catch potential of tropical Pacific fish stocks is projected to decline by up to 40% by the 2050s, relative to the 2000s; >50% of fishery-relevant species are projected to become locally extinct by 2100
- Marine heatwaves and events of high acid and low oxygen conditions can exacerbate the impact of long-term ocean warming, acidification and de-oxygenation on ecosystems and fisheries.

- The Arctic Ocean progresses faster by 10x (acidification) and 2x (warming) than the rest of the globe
- The Arctic Ocean currents are changing due to increased freshwater inputs and are invaded by the Atlantic and Pacific Oceans waters, which is leading to significant changes in the region's ecosystem.
- The Arctic Ocean summer sea ice may completely disappear by 2050, which along with the collapse of the Greenland Ice Sheet could have far-reaching consequences for climate, sea-level rise, and Arctic ecosystems.

- All European seas are becoming more acidic, warmer and less oxygenated with potential impacts on the marine ecosystem and human livelihoods.
- The Baltic Sea has been experiencing novel environmental conditions already, which have had profound effects on the region's ecology and fisheries.
- The North Sea, one of the most impacted regions in Europe, has already reached irreversible tipping points and undergone regime shifts due to factors such as overfishing, climate change, and pollution, leading to significant changes in the ecosystem and impacting the livelihoods of people who rely on it.

- CO₂ storage processes will weaken by the end of the 21st century impacting global temperatures and CO₂ uptake
- Hazardous, non-optimal living conditions for many marine organisms are projected to appear by 2030 and no later than 2038 with profound effects on regional ecosystems and food chains.
- Regime shifts in plankton communities are expected to occur by the end of the 21st century with potential impact on regional food chain

BACKGROUND

Human-induced climate change is causing significant harm to our oceans, with ocean acidification, warming, and deoxygenation posing fundamental threats to marine life and ultimately, human societies (Gruber, 2011; Schubert et al., 2006). These processes provide specific threats to marine ecosystems and increase the possibility of crossing tipping points: “critical thresholds beyond which a system reorganizes, often abruptly and/or irreversibly” (IPCC, 2022)^a. Once crossed, physical, chemical, and biological, changes may result in food web reorganisations and regime shifts triggering. These regime shifts, although regional, may add up to a problem of global dimensions for natural resources and human well-being.

To address these issues, the H2020 COMFORT project focused on investigating tipping points in the Earth system, specifically in relation to acidification, warming, and deoxygenation processes. The project aimed to assess safe operating spaces, mitigation pathways, and future scenarios. In this document, we present key findings from the COMFORT project and complement them with available literature on human-induced impacts on marine ecosystems, particularly in the Arctic, Atlantic, Pacific, and Southern Oceans, as well as in three European seas: the Mediterranean, Baltic, and North Sea.

GLOSSARY

Tipping-point: “A critical threshold beyond which a system reorganizes, often abruptly and/or irreversibly.”^a

Tipping Elements: “Large-scale components of the Earth system that may experience a regime shift if a tipping point is crossed.”^b

Regime shift: large, abrupt, persistent changes in the structure and function of ecosystems.^c

Figure1. Illustration of a shock-induced tipping point

Acidification

The ocean plays a crucial role in mitigating global warming by absorbing approximately 25% of the annual emissions of anthropogenic CO₂. However, this excess CO₂ has profound effects on the ocean’s chemistry: the more CO₂ it absorbs, the more acidic it becomes. Acidified waters harm many marine organisms such as e.g., warm and cold-water corals, and organisms that rely on optimum chemical conditions to build their calcium-based shells and other structures. Ocean acidity has increased at a pace faster than any known in Earth’s geologic past

Warming

Increasing global temperature due to greenhouse gases in the atmosphere results in oceanic surface waters’ heat uptake. Since 1970, the ocean has absorbed >90% of the extra heat, reducing climate change’s impact. However, higher temperature leading to detrimental living conditions for some marine organisms, such as tuna fish, as well as lower oxygen concentration (see deoxygenation), increased stratification*, and melting of sea ice and ice sheets, leading to changes in ocean circulation. Due to long-scale (hundreds of years) oceanic circulation processes, ocean warming is projected to continue, even if human-made greenhouse gas emissions stop immediately.

De-oxygenation

50% of the world’s oxygen is produced by the ocean. Yet, the ocean is losing its breath with a 2% decline in global oxygen (O₂) inventory between 1960-2010. This negative trend is predicted to increase further to 7% by 2100. Deoxygenation is most prominent in the coastal areas and is a result of primarily higher temperatures leading to lower O₂ solubility, increased stratification*, and excess of nutrients from agriculture runoff. Additionally, low-oxygen and oxygen-free ‘dead zones’, where most marine life cannot be supported, are also expected to expand.

*Stratification: separation of water column into upper and lower layers. In a strongly stratified water column mixing of layers is reduced, which lessens temperature, oxygen and nutrient exchange across layers.

Arctic Ocean

The Arctic environment faces multiple threats, making it one of the most vulnerable regions to climate change. Some abrupt changes that will likely occur within the century¹:

The climate change in the Arctic Ocean progresses 10x (acidification) and 2x (warming) faster than the rest of the globe

The Arctic environment is warming two times faster in the ocean² and four times faster in the atmosphere³ compared to the rest of the globe, with the air temperature increasing up to 10°C by the end of the century (compared to the 1985-2014 period^{1,4}). Furthermore, the Arctic marine ecosystem is enormously vulnerable to ocean acidification¹ with chemical changes up to ten times faster than those of the global ocean. Ocean acidification has, besides warming, the potential to substantially change the Arctic marine ecosystem⁵. Regional acidification is expected to worsen in the future^{6,7} leading to adverse effects on marine organisms that require to build their shells and other structures, such as calcifying plankton⁸, cold-water corals, and mussel reefs⁹.

The Arctic Ocean currents are changing due to increased freshwater inputs and are invaded by the waters from the Atlantic and Pacific Oceans

The warming of the Arctic Ocean and the subsequent inflow of freshwaters due to warming¹⁰ are changing ocean currents¹¹⁻¹⁴ with a progressive "invasion" by the Atlantic and Pacific domains, leading to the mixing of two distinct ecosystems¹⁵. Additionally, the Arctic Ocean is already shifting from light to nutrient limitation due to decreased sea ice cover and thus increased light availability. The consequences of these changes are detrimental and may trigger regional regime shifts in biological, physical-chemical properties.¹⁶⁻¹⁹

The Arctic Ocean is prone to an increased intensity and frequency of extreme events and summer-sea ice may completely disappear by 2050

Extreme events in the Arctic Ocean are expected to become more frequent and more intense, in particular in relation to summer sea-ice (which may even completely disappear by 2050²⁰), Greenland Ice Sheets loss²¹⁻²³, wildfires²⁴, and permafrost thaw²⁵. Such changes further alter the cycling of carbon and greenhouse gases (GHG)²⁶⁻²⁸ leading to a larger organic carbon export into the Arctic Ocean.

Atlantic Ocean

A tipping point in the North Atlantic Ocean currents lies at a temperature increase of up to $\sim 3.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ ²⁹, the current global warming is at $\sim 1.1^{\circ}\text{C}$ and is thus already within the lower bound of the critical range.

Weakening of the ocean currents would have climatic impacts on decadal timescales, leading to regional cooling and weather extremes over Europe and changes in global atmospheric circulation³⁰. These ocean currents are connected to the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) and their weakening may lead to an AMOC decline with significant changes in the Atlantic Ocean heat transport, Arctic sea ice extent and regional climate patterns.

Evidence indicates that a tipping point in the Atlantic was crossed during the recent preindustrial period, suggesting its vulnerability to the present-day effects of climate change

The northern North Atlantic Ocean circulation crossed a tipping point during the 13th and 14th centuries as revealed by recent reconstructions of the marine environment.³¹ This subpolar North Atlantic destabilisation in the past led to a rapid weakening of the regional ocean circulation and regional climate change across several centuries.³¹ These changes were associated with freshwater input from melting glaciers and Arctic sea ice, processes now occurring at an accelerated rate.¹ This highlights that melting sea ice in the North Atlantic has the potential to cause rapid and long-lasting regional climate change.

Implementation of the Carbon Dioxide Removal methods after temporarily exceeding the Paris Agreement temperature targets could lead to pronounced cooling in the subpolar North Atlantic with significant negative centennial impacts on the surrounding regions

The consequences of carbon dioxide removal techniques (CDR) are being examined, as they are currently seen as required to reach the IPCC Paris Agreement. CDR technologies are not yet fully developed and lack clear plans for large-scale implementations³²⁻³⁴. Yet, emitting, and subsequently removing CO_2 from the atmosphere could lead to significant centennial changes, such as extreme cooling in the subpolar North Atlantic and amplified temperature fluctuations³⁵. This would have considerable consequences for the Arctic sea ice, permafrost extent, and high-latitude ecosystems. Therefore, not emitting CO_2 into the atmosphere is preferable over post-emission CO_2 removal.

European seas

The Strait of Gibraltar and the Mediterranean Sea region are more acidic, warmer and thus less oxygenated than the Atlantic Ocean

Coastal waters in the Strait of Gibraltar are more acidic than the open Atlantic Ocean waters as observed in the last 40 years.^{36,37} This trend is especially detrimental to cold-water corals in these regions. Furthermore, the Mediterranean Sea is expected to become not only more acidic, but also warmer, and thus have lower oxygen concentrations in particular in the Eastern Mediterranean Sea basin^{38,39}, affecting marine organisms and their habitats.

The Baltic Sea will experience novel environmental conditions and regime shifts

The Baltic Sea is projected to become warmer which can lead to the emergence of novel environmental conditions that communities never experienced before, leading to new ecosystem functioning⁴⁰. This may impact regional food web dynamics, e.g. cod, sprat and herring stocks.^{41,42} Novel conditions and communities are increasingly appearing in the Baltic Sea⁴³ and are expected to increase in the future.⁴⁴

The North Sea as one of the most impacted regions has already experienced tipping points and regime shifts

The North Sea, amongst the Baltic and Mediterranean Seas, is one of the heaviest impacted marine ecosystems by human activities in the world for centuries. As a result, tipping points and irreversible regime shifts have already occurred in e.g. 1980⁴⁵ and 2003⁴⁶ when the community completely restructured due to climate change and overfishing. Currently, the water mass circulation of the North Sea is projected to experience an abrupt

change between 2030 and 2040, leading to the exemplification of regional acidification in bottom waters starting from 2050 and in surface waters, starting from 2070 under the high emission (RCP8.5, business-as-usual) scenario^{47,48}. The freshwater inputs from Arctic Sea ice loss⁴⁸ and the Baltic Sea waters entering the region are potentially the main driver for such changes leading to changes in circulation and water mass exchange. The changes in the North Sea will heavily impact the regional ecosystem functioning⁴⁹ and food resource.⁵⁰

Southern Ocean

CO₂ storage processes will weaken by the end of the 21st century impacting global temperatures and CO₂ uptake

Sea-ice loss due to global warming is projected to weaken the CO₂ storage processes in the Weddell Sea, Southern Ocean by the end of the 21st century through increased outgassing in autumn and winter. Furthermore, freshwater inputs from decreased sea ice are projected to alter water mass circulation in the region.⁵¹ Due to the Southern Ocean's critical role in CO₂ and excess heat uptake, these regional changes will have an impact on the global heat and CO₂ uptake and storage.

Hazardous, living conditions for many marine organisms are projected to appear in the 2030s

Increasing CO₂ atmospheric emissions cause enhanced CO₂ oceanic uptake leading to more hazardous, acidified waters. These unfavourable conditions are projected to appear by 2030 and no later than 2038 under the RCP 8.5 scenario in the Southern Ocean⁵²⁻⁵⁴ impacting the functioning of the regional ecosystem.

By the year 2038

Regime shifts in plankton communities are expected to occur by the end of the 21st century

Climate warming is projected to decouple the silicate (bioessential micronutrient) biological property and physical property in the Southern Ocean by the end of the 21st century⁵⁵. These properties define the region of high abundance of silicate-dependent phytoplankton organisms, yet warming is projected to shift the silicate property southwards by the end of the 21st century in the RCP 8.5 scenario**. The front decoupling may lead to regime shifts in phytoplankton community structure and impact biological CO₂ uptake in the Southern Ocean^{56,57} and thus global CO₂ uptake.

**RCP 8.5: The representative Concentration Pathways, high emission, business-as-usual global warming scenario.

Pacific Ocean

Marine heatwaves, events of exceptionally acid conditions and low oxygen levels can, individually or in combination, exacerbate the impact of long-term ocean acidification, warming, and de-oxygenation on ecosystems and fisheries.

The California current system is particularly prone to acidification extremes events whilst in the Eastern Pacific region extreme deoxygenation events compress the habitat by up to 70% (locally over 80%). The extreme events are associated with the deaths of e.g. sea snakes, octopuses and crabs – and coral bleaching around the Pacific island nations⁵⁸ and physiological changes to Pacific herring in the northwest Pacific.⁵⁹ In addition, harmful algal blooms triggered by MHWs have led to fish deaths in South Australia.⁶⁰ These episodic events can provide a window into the future, as the long-term oxygen loss might transform current “extreme” conditions into the future normal state.

The maximum catch potential of tropical Pacific fish stocks is projected to decline by up to 40% by the 2050s under the RCP8.5 emissions scenario, relative to the 2000s; more than half of fishery-relevant species are projected to become locally extinct by 2100 due to ocean acidification, warming, and deoxygenation and sea-level rise⁶¹

**40% decline
by 2050**

Many substantial predicted biological and socio-economic impacts on tropical fisheries can be prevented if GHG mitigation actions keep global atmospheric warming below 1.5 °C relative to pre-industrial levels.

REFERENCES

1. IPCC, 2018: Annex I: Glossary [Matthews, J.B.R. (ed.)]. In: *Global Warming of 1.5°C. An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the threat of climate change, sustainable development, and efforts to eradicate poverty* [Masson-Delmotte, V., P. Zhai, H.-O. Pörtner, D. Roberts, J. Skea, P.R. Shukla, A. Pirani, W. Moufouma-Okia, C. Péan, R. Pidcock, S. Connors, J.B.R. Matthews, Y. Chen, X. Zhou, M.I. Gomis, E. Lonnoy, T. Maycock, M. Tignor, and T. Waterfield (eds.)]. In Press
2. Lenton, et al., 2008, PNAS (<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0705414105>)
3. Biggs R, T Blenckner, C Folke, L Gordon, A Norström, M Nyström, GD Peterson. 2012. Regime Shifts. In: *Encyclopedia of Theoretical Ecology*. A Hastings, L Gross (eds). University of California Press, Ewing, NJ, USA.
4. AMAP Assessment (2018). Arctic Ocean Acidification, (AMAP), Tromsø, Norway, 2018.
5. Shu et al., 2022, Science Advances (<https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abn9755>)
6. Rantanen et al. 2020, Communications Earth & Environment (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-022-00498-3>)
7. Isaksen et al., 2022, Scientific Reports (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-13568-5>)
8. Gaylord et al., 2015, Ecological Society of America (<https://doi.org/10.1890/14-0802.1>)
9. Terhaar et al., 2021, Biogeosciences (<https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-18-2221-2021>)
10. Orr et al., 2022, Nature (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-05205-y>.)
11. Brodie et al. 2014, Ecology and Evolution (<https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.1105>)
12. Sunday et al., 2017, Nature Climate Change (<https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate3161>)
13. Solomon et al., 2021, Ocean Science (<https://doi.org/10.5194/os-17-1081-2021>)
14. Kelly et al., 2020, Earth's Future (<https://doi.org/10.1029/2019EF001394>)
15. Wefing et al., 2021, Ocean Science (<https://doi.org/10.5194/os-17-111-2021>)
16. Wilson et al. 2021, Communications Earth & Environment (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-021-00237-0>)
17. Oziel et al., 2022, Global Biogeochemical Cycles (<https://doi.org/10.1029/2021GB007268>)
18. Ingvaldsen et al., 2021, Nature Reviews Earth & Environment (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-021-00228-x>)
19. Polyakov et al., 2020, Frontiers in Marine Sciences (<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2020.00491>.)
20. Drinkwater et al., 2021, ICES Journal of Marine Science (<https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsab182>)
21. Vernet et al., 2020, Frontiers in Marine Science (<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00583>)
22. Oziel et al., 2020, Nature Communications (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-15485-5>)
23. Sigmond et al., 2018, Nature Climate Change (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-018-0124-y>)
24. Boers and Rypdal, 2021, PNAS (<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.202419211>)

22. The IMBIE Team, 2020, *Nature* (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-019-1855-2>)
23. Stranne et al., 2021, *Communications Earth & Environment* (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-021-00140-8>)
24. Witze 2020, *Nature* (<https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-02568-y>)
25. Schuur et al., 2022, *Annual review of Environment and Resources* (<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-012220-011847>)
26. Hugelius et al., 2020, *PNAS* (<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1916387117>)
27. Steinbach et al. 2021, *PNAS* (<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2019672118>)
28. Miner et al., 2022, *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment* (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-021-00230-3>)
29. Collins M, et al., 2019: *Extremes, Abrupt Changes and Managing Risk*. In: *IPCC Special Report on the Ocean and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate* [H.-O. Pörtner, D.C. Roberts, V. Masson-Delmotte, P. Zhai, M. Tignor, E. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Nicolai, A. Okem, J. Petzold, B. Rama, N.M. Weyer (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA, pp. 589-655. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157964.008>
30. Swingedouw et al., 2021, *ANNALS of The New York Academy of Science* (<https://doi.org/10.1111/nyas.14659>)
31. Arellano-Nava et al. 2022, *Nature Communications* (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-32653-x>)
32. Minx et al., 2018, *Environmental Research Letters* ([10.1088/1748-9326/aabf9b](https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aabf9b))
33. Fuss et al., 2018, *Environmental Research Letters* ([10.1088/1748-9326/aabf9f](https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aabf9f))
34. Nemet et al., 2018, *Environmental Research Letters* ([10.1088/1748-9326/aabff4](https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aabff4))
35. Schwinger et al., 2022 *Nature Communications* (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-28573-5>)
36. Padin et al., 2020, *Earth System Science Data* (<https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-12-2647-2020>)
37. García-Lafuente et al., 2021, *Frontiers in Marine Science* (<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.613444>)
38. Reale et al., 2022, *Biogeosciences* (<https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-19-4035-2022>)
39. Solidoro et al., 2022, *Frontiers in Marine Science* (<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.781522>)
40. Pandolfi et al., 2020, *Science*, <https://doi.org/10.2307/2260525>
41. Meier et al., 2022a, *Earth System Dynamics* (<https://doi.org/10.5194/esd-13-457-2022>)
42. Möllmann et al., 2021, *Scientific Reports* (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-93843-z>)
43. Ammar et al., 2020, *Global Change Biology* (<https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15503>)
44. Blenckner et al., 2021, *Frontiers in Marine Science* (<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.745722>)
45. Beaugrand et al., 2004, *Communications Biology* (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-022-04100-6>)
46. Sguotti et al., 2022, *Frontiers in Marine Science* (<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.945204>)
47. McGovern et al. 2022. *Ocean Acidification*. In: OSPAR, 2023: The 2023 Quality Status Report for the North-East Atlantic. OSPAR Commission, London. Available at: <https://oap.ospar.org/en/ospar-assessments/quality-status-reports/qsr-2023/other-assessments/ocean-acidification>
48. Holt et al., 2008, *Journal of Geophysical Research Ocean* (<https://doi.org/10.1029/2006JC004034>)
49. Vermaat et al., 2008, *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2008.07.005>)
50. Squotti et al., 2022, *Reference Module in Earth Systems and Environmental Sciences* (<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-90798-9.00004-4>)
51. Nissen et al., 2022, *Nature Communications* (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-30671-3>)
52. Mcneil and Matear, 2008, *PNAS* (<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0806318105>)
53. Kwiatkowski and Orr, 2018, *Nature Climate Change* (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-017-0054-0>)
54. Krumhardt et al., 2019, *Journal of Advances in Modelling Earth Systems* (<https://doi.org/10.1029/2018MS001483>)
55. Freeman et al., 2018, *Global Biogeochemical Cycles* (<https://doi.org/10.1029/2017GB005816>)
56. John et al., 2015, *Geophysical Research Letters* (<https://doi.org/10.1002/2015GL066160>)
57. Henson et al., 2021, *Nature Communications* (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-25699-w>)
58. Holbrook et al., 2022, *Nature Reviews Earth and Environment* (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-020-0068-4>)
59. Villalobos et al., 2020, *Frontiers in Marine Science* (<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2020.597899>)
60. Roberts et al., 2019, *Frontiers in Marine Science* (<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00610>)
61. Lam et al., 2020, *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment* (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-020-0071-9>)

Authors: Dagmara Rusiecka^{1,2}, Thorsten Blenckner³, Christoph Heinze^{1,2}, Helena Martins⁴, Precious Mongwe⁵, Beatriz Arellano Nava⁶, Paul Halloran⁶, Laurent Ozier⁷, Helen Powley⁸

- 1 Geophysical Institute, University of Bergen, Bergen, 5020, Norway
- 2 Bjerknes Centre for Climate Research, University of Bergen, Bergen, 5020, Norway
- 3 Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholms Universitet, 10691, Sweden
- 4 Rossby Centre, Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute, 60176 Norrköping, Sweden
- 5 Council for Scientific and Industrial Research, Cape Town, South Africa
- 6 Global Systems Institute and Geography Department, University of Exeter, Exeter, United Kingdom
- 7 Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung, Bremerhaven, 27570, Germany
- 8 Plymouth Marine Laboratory, Plymouth, PL1 3DH, United Kingdom

Cover photo credit: Svein Østerhus, NORCE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820989 (project COMFORT, Our common future ocean in the Earth system – quantifying coupled cycles of carbon, oxygen, and nutrients for determining and achieving safe operating spaces with respect to tipping points). The work reflects only the author's/authors' view; the European Commission and their executive agency are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information the work contains.

